

NEW NORMAL HOME VISITATION: A TRANSCENDENTAL PHENOMENOLOGY THROUGH THE LENS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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NEW NORMAL HOME VISITATION: A TRANSCENDENTAL PHENOMENOLOGY THROUGH THE LENS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study is a qualitative research using the transcendental phenomenological design which aims to understand teachers' experiences of Baybay City Senior High School on home visitation in the new normal. There were inclusion and exclusion criteria in choosing the participants. Semi-structured interview schedules with open-ended questions were utilized. Based from the results, the four emergent themes were generated which include roll with the punches which characterize how teachers deal with challenges, sailing seasons show the willingness to work in a specific condition, triggered emotions talk about the reaction towards memories and experiences, cover a lot of ground refers to the contributed information. For the roll with the punches the sub-themes are forked road; difficulty in location, thief of time; teachers' wasted time due to passive students, throw caution to the wind; health risks, dicey situation; safety risks, and from a to z; the unending tasks of teachers. For sailing seasons, the sub-themes are taken under your wing; drop in the bucket; strategy used, and change of heart; response to teachers' effort. For triggered emotions the sub-themes are cloud nine; fulfillment, heart of gold; affectionate, and edge of seat; flabbergasted. In terms of cover a lot of ground the sub-themes are apple of one's eye; own choice and fine wine; appropriateness. The study showed that teachers have positive emotions towards home visitation. They had difficult experiences but they were able to manage it. Home visitation experiences were beneficial because it provides lifelong lessons for the teachers.

Keywords: *Home visitation, Teachers experiences, New normal*

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INTRODUCTION

Prior to the onset of pandemic, home visitation is an intervention employed by teachers to minimize the frequency of absences among the students. Through home visits, teachers were aware of the circumstances and activities that contributed to the absences and the lack of motivation of the students. Corresponding to the ideas presented by Wright (2018), the primary reasons why students lack motivation to attend classes were lack of essential skills, such as basic academic skills, cognitive strategies, and academic-enabler skills, resulting in incomplete assigned work. Furthermore, more effort is needed to complete the assigned work despite having the necessary skills; and the presence of classroom instruction and learning activities that do not engage them. Moreover, failure to perceive an adequate payoff for completing the assigned work, such as praise, access to rewards, or to motivate greater effort; and the most common is lack of positive relationship with the teacher were the reasons.

The purpose of home visitation as Terziev (2017) said is to build trust and improve educational achievements. Engagement with families outside of school facilitates shared comprehension and demonstrates teachers' concern for the students. A relationship of trust can motivate parents to become involved in their children's education, resulting in improvements in attendance, behavior, and academic performance. In addition, he emphasizes that home visitation provide teachers with the opportunity to learn more about their students' origins, hobbies, and life experiences, which they can subsequently use to enhance their teaching. Thus, the perspective of Yilmaz (2019) presents that teacher home visitation positively affect student attitude. Using teacher reflections, interviews, and student self-reported data, it appears that teacher home visits influence students' attitudes toward school and the classes they are enrolled in. Based on Parent Teacher Home Visits (2016), teachers who schedule home visits gain insight into how this form of communication can improve student performance.

As the educational landscape changes to modular learning, home visitation was intensified. Home visitation refers to teachers visiting students in their homes and meeting with their parents as defined by Junco (2021) to identify the challenges that their struggling children have experienced. It is important to track the progress of the students in order to get to know them. It also assists teachers in determining the needs and progress of their students and establish positive communication and relationships with their families to provide further support. Teachers will be able to observe the real-life situations of each student and their family during home visits. Teachers can use this method to foster communication, form relationships, and provide help to struggling families. Parents' involvement in their children's education should be increased. The involvement of parents in their children's education is critical. Every parent or guardian must help their children learn throughout this period. Parents will be encouraged to support their children's educational needs through home visits. Positive outcomes may result from strong cooperation between parents and schools. Moreover, as supported by Zambarrano (2021) parents who are concerned about their children's educational needs support the school's programs, activities, and projects. Conducting home visits during this time may be difficult and may put one at risk of contracting COVID-19, but prioritizing one's own and others' health by following correct health standards may result in a productive and safe home visitation.

Thus, home visitation is the Department of Education's response when a student is exhibiting absenteeism or is on the verge of dropping out of school. The adviser provides necessary interventions including but not limited to home visitation to learners who are absent for five consecutive days and/or those at risk of dropping out, as evidence in the reminder to teachers reflected at the bottom of School Form 2 (SF2), also known as the Daily Attendance Report of Learners. With this, Pascual (2021) asserts that teachers should view home visitation as a solution rather than a practice. Teachers may also believe that not all students are deserving of home visits, but only those who have a proclivity to drop out, are low-performing, and have a history of chronic absenteeism.

Learners are given a specified time range in which to complete their assigned assignments. They are given flexibility in completing each module based on their learning needs, characteristics, and degree of knowledge to guarantee that they have gained mastery of the learning materials, which is also a precondition for success in subsequent modules. Teachers use tactics that consider the settings and diversity of learners' readiness, learning interests, and learning profiles (Guan, A.J., 2021).

There are benefits of home visitation as Ilhan, et al. (2019) show that the post-test score following the implementation of reading classes during home visitation demonstrates the benefit of home visits. This shows that the reading performance has improved as a result of the restricted face-to-face reading classes conducted through home visits. This is agreed by Rodado (2021) who posits that the teacher should determine the students' reading level and provide appropriate reading materials for their level, as well as frequent follow-up and home visits to improve their reading comprehension skills. Thus, Pascual (2021) presents that the majority of home visits are for follow-ups on students who are committing absenteeism and are on the verge of dropping out.

Statement of the Problem

Baybay City Senior High School has 95 teachers who were conducting home visitation simultaneously every week to struggling students in their respective subject area. Teachers were dealing with individually unique learners. This study is being thought of to describe the experiences of the teachers conducting home visitation of the struggling students in senior high school and looked into the students' behavior, academic achievement, parent involvement, students' attitude and motivation.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used Edmund Husserl (1931) qualitative research approach using the transcendental phenomenology. It is relevant in this study because it described accurately the structure of the phenomenon. It also uncovered particular experience and how they deal with it through semi-structured interview utilizing maximum variation. The teachers described their experiences objectively and then reflect on the description with reference to the existing theories. It is also designed to gain understanding of how teachers think during the conduct of the home visitation and this expanded our knowledge about the phenomenon.

As cited in Bliss (2016), phenomenological approach provides deep investigation of what experiences mean to people. In addition, it concerns with the inquiry of human experiences specified in Collins & Rocco (2015) in order to learn people's common sense of understanding and the meaning they make of their experiences. This also set aside prejudices and priori assumptions.

Research Setting

This study was conducted in Baybay City Senior High School located at Zone 12, 30 de Diciembre St. City of Baybay (Google map: 10°40'33.0"N 124°48'11.6"E) during the pre-interview and participants chose their desired location for the final interview. Baybay City Senior High School is a stand-alone school offering the different tracks such as Academic track, Arts and Design track, and Technical Vocational and Livelihood track. The Academic track is composed of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy and Business Management (ABM), General Academic (GA), and HUMSS. In addition, TVL offers different

majors such as Electrical Installation, Agriculture, Hairdressing, Home Economics, ICT and Tailoring. On the other hand, Arts and Design offers Music, Theatre, Arts, and Dance. The institution has 95 teachers and 2249 enrollees for the school year 2021-2022. These students are from different areas of Baybay City with varied academic performance. These are struggling students who have difficulty in understanding the lesson, need clear instruction of the activity, low performing in class, and non-submission of activities. In the conduct of the study, the teacher had the option to choose a comfortable place other than the school to share his/her experience through interview.

Research Participants

The chosen participants were selected based on the inclusion criteria to ensure precise data collection and accurate results. This involves identifying and selecting individuals that are knowledgeable about phenomenon or interest as emphasized by Cresswell & Plano Clark (2011).

Inclusion criteria include teacher participants who were subject teachers or advisers. They were the teachers who have experienced conducting home visitation to struggling students. Participants were from different departments such as Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL), Accountancy and business Management (ABM), Arts & Design (A&D), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), General Academic (GA), and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). Omona (2013) explained that the researcher should collect data that reaches saturation, theoretical saturation, or informational redundancy. Agreeable to Wa-Mbaleka and Gladstone (2018), a minimum of eight participants are needed, however, if you have not reached the data saturation point, there is a need to add more participants to get the trend and pattern.

In relation to this, participants that adhered in the inclusion criteria were those who were interested to be a participant of the study during the preliminary interview. An informed consent was given to participants to determine their willingness to participate. Individuals who have expressed interest and met the criteria for participating in the study were chosen based on age range from 21-55, gender (male, female, and LGBTQ); and their experience with the phenomenon of home visitation to senior high students. The age range is 21-55 because it is the common age among the teachers in Baybay City Senior High School. These details were based on the data they put on the interview schedule.

Exclusion includes teachers who were not present during the scheduled interview, have numerous reasons for their absence, responded to the interview in a hurried manner, and are afflicted by comorbidities. But, in this study, the additional participants as replacement declined because they reasoned out that their knowledge was not enough and they were not confident to share it with others. From the pre-interview there were eight (8) teachers and four (4) reserved teachers who agreed to be my participants, but due to some personal reasons, only five (5) teachers confirmed that they could attend the final interview at Raileighs Baybay. I had considered and respected the decision of the seven (7) teachers who refused to be my participants for the final interview. The participants who confirmed their attendance plotted their own free time and day for the final interview. Three participants chose lunch time and the two participants chose snack time. I was exhausted to invite other participants even though I told them that all expenses were incurred by me, also in the course of the conduct of the study the data has saturated.

In the following paragraphs the study participants are introduced to give description to the reader thus having better understanding on each participant's profile.

Participant No. 1

Teacher 01 is the code name of Participant No. 1. She is a graduate of BS in Food Technology and took Education units at St. Michael of Hindang Leyte. She is teaching Practical Research, 3 I's, and Research Capstone. She has been teaching for more than 10 years, five years in a prestige university and five years in DepEd. She is into research and presented researches every year during

the Research Conference. She provides support and assistance to senior high school teachers who are interested in conducting research. She is a witty person with a pleasant personality and good communication skills. She is an empowered mother and a caring wife.

Participant No. 2

Teacher 02 is the code name of Participant No. 2. A graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics. He is teaching General Mathematics and Statistics. He has a golden voice and he loves to sing. He is passionate of being a teacher because he consistently comes to school as early as 6:30am. He is a workaholic that is why he loves to report to school early so that he can still do a lot of paper works before the class begin. He has been in the teaching profession for 15 years. Aside from being a teacher, he has a skill in photography. He accepts bookings for photography every weekend and holidays. He is also a math wizard where every student looks up to him because of his unique way of teaching Math subjects.

Participant No. 3

Teacher 03 is the code name of Participant No. 3. She is a Food Technology graduate and took her education units at EVSU Ormoc. She is a keen observer and active listener. She has been in teaching for four years. She is one of the teachers who shows support to school activities and actively engages herself to help. She is a sweet person because everyone likes her personality. Approachable and willing to listen to your sentiments and concerns.

Participant No. 4

Teacher 04 is the code name of Participant No. 4. She is a DOST scholar and been teaching in DepEd for more than 5 years now. A graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Biological Science. She provides technical assistance to teachers and generously shares her expertise. Teacher 04 is notably good in singing. She is a loving mother of two children.

Participant No. 5

Teacher 05 is the code name of Participant No. 5. A graduate of education major in Physical Science. She is a competitive person. It is manifested through her actions because even though she was still new in the teaching profession, she could do things excellently. She is remarkably known for being patient, kind, and a friend to all. She has good communication and social skills. She can get along easily with other teachers and open to share insights about teaching.

Research Instruments

A semi-structured interview schedule with open-ended questions were utilized based on few key questions but allowed the interviewer some freedom to delve deeper into the subject. Semi-structured interview is usually one in which the interviewer has a check list of questions that the participant is asked to address. It often starts with more general questions or topics and arguably many questions emerge during the interview within a pre-set general framework (Harvey, 2020).

In this study as supported by DeJonckheere (2019), the method allows to collect open-ended data, to explore participant's thoughts, feelings, beliefs about a particular topic and to delve deeply into personal and sometimes sensitive issues.

Data Analysis Procedure

This study utilized a Thematic Analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006) in interpreting the answers of the participants. Thematic analysis is theoretically flexible which means it can be used within different framework to answer different types of research questions. It is also an excellent

way of discovering subjective meanings and interpretations that people give to their experiences. Transcription of the audio-video recording was the first step in analyzing the data followed by the six-phase process of reflexive thematic analysis which are familiarization with the data, coding, generating initial themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up (Braun, V. & Clarke, V., 2019).

As explained by Kiger & Varpio 2020, thematic analysis seeks to understand experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across data set. Thus, after the data were gathered, I used Thematic analysis to interpret the narrative data from my participants. I clearly outlined their paradigmatic orientation and assumption to ensure trustworthiness of my findings and interpretation. The audio-video responses were transcribed according to the teachers experiences on home visitation in the new normal.

First step is familiarization of data, I have familiarized the data, transcribed the familiar data set as advised by (Braun & Clarke 2006). I familiarized the data set by reviewing and listening to the recordings several times so that I would be oriented to the commonalities and differences in the answers of the participants. I extracted and encoded significant statements in the dendrogram. I translated the responses of the participants from vernacular to English without changing the conveyed message. I did it during dawn because there was no distractions.

Second step is coding of data, I did the generating of codes manually. Given emphasis by Nowell, et al. (2017), code should be sufficiently well-defined and demarcated such that it does not overlap with other codes and fit within a larger coding framework. I labelled the data into specific code names to make it more meaningful to read while considering the connection between items in order to understand the data in preparation for developing themes. There were 20 code names created.

Third step is generating themes, I have noticed the patterns as the codes are being used again. I examined the collated data and developed themes of broader significance. I constructed the theme using idiomatic expression and metaphors that correlates to the answers of my participants. These themes provided significant link of the participants' responses. The themes created were Roll with the Punches, Sailing Seasons, Triggered Emotions, and Cover a lot of Ground.

Fourth step is reviewing themes, I created a narrative description for the themes through refining the most important aspect to create a coherent narrative which provides insights. As expressed in Braun & Clarke (2006), the data within each theme should have adequate commonality and coherence.

Fifth step is defining and naming themes, I reviewed the names of themes to be included in the final data to ensure they are brief and adequately descriptive. Themes were splitted, combined, or discarded to attain desired themes. I carefully refined each aspect of each theme.

Sixth step is writing up themes, I developed a detailed analysis of each theme focusing on the scope of the suitable theme. I kept on omitting and changing the description of themes until I arrived at a very acceptable analysis of themes. I weaved together the analytic narrative and data extracts regarding teachers' experiences on home visitation. I wrote the general findings from all data collected from the transcribed statements of the teachers. With these, I interpreted the results from the data being gathered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Home Visitation Experiences

The results of this study present the experiences of teachers on home visitation in Baybay City Senior High School amidst the pandemic. The study used thematic analysis in interpreting and analysing qualitative data. As supported by the idea of Caulfield (2019) and Bogdan & Biklen (2007), results were examined and identified common themes-ideas, topics, and meanings that came up repeatedly. Direct quotations were used to resonate with the explicit responses of the participants where their perspectives are openly displayed. The results of the interview were analysed and themes were classified to several subthemes according to the research questions as emerged during the transcription of data set which were derived from the significant statements verbalized by the research participants. A dendrogram was used to present each theme, sub-theme, and significant statements comprehensively.

Home visitation gives avenue for teachers to talk with parents about the students' performance in school. It demonstrates concern for the students' well-being and serves as reassurance. It also facilitates communication across cultural boundaries and removes potential obstacles to the learning of the students. During the semi-structured interview utilizing maximum variation, teachers' perspectives were expressed following this question: What are your experiences on home visitation? The responses were collected from the widest range of perspectives from the participants. I have gained a more wholistic view analyzed from different standpoints.

The participants revealed different experiences on conducting home visitation. Based on the data gathered, these are the four emergent themes which were reflected from the teachers' experiences. First, Roll with the Punches which has five sub-themes, these are forked road, thief of time, throw caution to the wind, dicey situation, and from a to z. Second is Sailing Seasons which has three sub-themes, these are taken under your wing, drop in the bucket, and change of heart. Third is Triggered Emotions which has three sub-themes, cloud nine, heart of gold, and edge of seat. Fourth is Cover a lot of Ground which has two sub-themes, apple of one's eye and fine wine.

Figure 1. Themes and Sub-themes

The participants revealed different experiences on conducting home visitation. Based on the data gathered, these are the four emergent themes which were reflected from the teachers' experiences. First, (a) Roll with the Punches which has five sub-themes, these are forked road, thief of time, throw caution to the wind, dicey situation, and a to z. Second, (b) Sailing Seasons which has three sub-themes, these are taken under your wing, drop in the bucket, and change of heart. Third, (c) Triggered Emotions which has three sub-themes, cloud nine, heart of gold, and

edge of seat. Fourth, (d) Cover a lot of Ground which has two sub-themes, apple of one's eye and fine wine.

Teachers deal with challenges but still give meaningful learning to students. During the pandemic, it was difficult for teachers to determine the precise location of their students. They only provided the name of the barangay and did not provide any additional information about it. Teachers had a hard time finding their students. Students who had not turned in their work despite being notified of their status were given another opportunity to do so before the deadline. Students who were working were also given an extension to comply with the requirements for their missing outputs. On the other hand, students who did not participate in any way and did not hand in any work were graded with a failing grade. This was due to the fact that the maximum extension of the deadline was granted, but no action was taken. Failed students were showing signs of laziness based from the records of the teachers.

Giving follow-up to students helped them accomplish better adhering to scheduled submission. The home visitation experiences were really beneficial and provided lifelong lessons that can be applied to a variety of situations in the future. Not only did they learn to engage more with students in the learning process, but they also learned to engage more with parents. They gained the ability to be flexible and adaptable.

Teachers have positive emotions towards home visitation. They found it difficult but they were able to formulate ways how to beat it. The experiences of teachers on home visitation has contributed a lot of information and facts. Nothing in this world can be relied upon to stay constant. We are able to endure and thrive in this ever-changing environment because we are adaptable and flexible.

CONCLUSION

These experiences encountered by the participants can be considered as educational inputs. These are useful in innovating the scope approaches of home visitation program. Teachers can look for the brighter side of the home visitation that they can be grateful for. The participants' responses dominated with the challenges they encountered on home visitation. It serves as a guide for teachers on how to be positive in the most challenging situation. Peer mentoring is useful also in collaborating and exchanging of ideas on how to deal with struggling students.

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